

Leveraging Smart Sentry to Detect and Mitigate Cyber Threats in Industrial IoT Networks

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Abstract – The Internet of Things (IoT) has revolutionized digital connectivity but has simultaneously broadened the landscape for cyber threats. This paper focuses on categorizing IoT attacks by integrating multiple machine learning (ML) models and deep learning (DL) techniques. The research presents a binary and multiclass classification approach utilizing algorithms like Random Forest, Decision Tree, Extra Trees Classifier, Support Vector Machine, k-Nearest Neighbors, and a Deep Neural Network. Experiments were conducted using the Edge-IIoTset dataset, reflecting real-world IoT threat scenarios. Pre-processing involved Principal Component Analysis (PCA) for dimensionality reduction, Synthetic Minority Over-sampling Technique (SMOTE) to counteract class imbalance, and data normalization. The study provides a comparative analysis of model performance, showing that the DNN model achieved outstanding results—100% accuracy for binary classification, 96.15% for 6-class classification, and 94.68% for 15-class classification. A 10-fold cross-validation was also implemented to ensure model generalization. The findings offer valuable insights for improving the security posture of IoT environments through intelligent detection mechanisms.

Index Terms – Internet of Things, Machine Learning, Security, Intrusion detection system.

I. INTRODUCTION

The integration of IoT into everyday operations has fostered an interconnected world, enabling devices, infrastructure, and users to communicate seamlessly. This digital transformation has introduced significant operational efficiency but has also expanded the potential attack surface, making IoT ecosystems a prime target for cyber adversaries. The diversity of devices, resource constraints, and lack of unified security protocols further exacerbate these vulnerabilities. In industrial settings, IIoT infrastructures face advanced threats ranging from ransomware and malware to denial-of-service (DoS) and phishing campaigns. These attacks jeopardize system integrity, interrupt production workflows, and threaten sensitive data. Addressing these risks calls for robust, adaptable cybersecurity frameworks. Machine learning has emerged as a promising avenue to enhance IoT security

by autonomously detecting anomalies and attack patterns. However, deploying ML algorithms directly on resource-constrained IoT devices remains challenging due to computational and power limitations. Moreover, conventional rule-based security systems often fall short against sophisticated modern threats. This paper proposes an intelligent intrusion detection approach tailored to IoT networks' complex and dynamic environments.

II. RELATED WORKS

The field of intrusion detection in IoT and IIoT systems has seen significant research, particularly with the growing reliance on machine learning (ML) and deep learning (DL) techniques. The Edge-IIoTset dataset, introduced by Ferrag et al. [1], was developed using a realistic IIoT testbed comprising diverse devices, protocols, and network configurations. The dataset captures a wide variety of cyberattacks, including malware, MITM, and DoS, providing a benchmark for evaluating ML and federated learning-based IDS frameworks. Gupta et al. [2] presented an IDS model for IoMT networks based on Decision Trees. Utilizing the UNSW-NB15 dataset, their model achieved an accuracy of 94.23%, outperforming several traditional IDSs in detecting malicious IoMT traffic.

Cheikhrouhou et al. [7] conducted a comprehensive review of IDS strategies for IIoT networks, emphasizing the challenges posed by device heterogeneity, resource constraints, and the necessity for real-time detection. Their findings suggest that ML-based IDSs outperform signature and anomaly-based systems but also highlighted issues related to scalability and energy consumption. Elias et al. [10] proposed a hybrid CNN-LSTM model for IIoT edge environments. The system processes both spatial and temporal traffic patterns and is privacy-aware, making it well-suited for edge networks. The model demonstrated high accuracy rates, achieving 97.14% on multiclass classification tasks. Khacha et al. [13] introduced a deep learning-based IDS for IIoT by combining CNN and RNN layers, which excelled at capturing both spatial and sequential features, enhancing detection capabilities in industrial systems.

Friha et al. [6] proposed a decentralized IDS utilizing federated learning and differential privacy. Their model improves intrusion detection accuracy while addressing privacy concerns in IIoT applications. Bhandari et al. [3] put forth a distributed DNN architecture deployed across edge devices and gateways, enabling scalable detection of cyber threats in smart IoT ecosystems. This distributed approach reduced latency while maintaining high detection rates. While many studies offer high accuracy for specific attack categories or device types, they often struggle to generalize across diverse IIoT infrastructures and attack variations. SmartSentry addresses this limitation by maintaining high performance metrics across binary and multiclass classifications without increasing architectural complexity, making it highly adaptable to dynamic IIoT settings.

III. DATASET DESCRIPTION

The Edge-IIoTset dataset is a comprehensive and diverse collection of data specifically curated for applications in Edge Computing within Industrial Internet of Things (IIoT) environments. It is designed to emulate realistic industrial scenarios by capturing a wide array of data points from various IoT devices, sensors, and systems typically deployed in industrial sectors. This dataset reflects both standard operational states and a multitude of cyberattack scenarios, offering a robust foundation for tasks such as intrusion detection, anomaly detection, and predictive maintenance. The Edge-IIoTset comprises data collected from multiple sensors—such as ultrasonic sensors, pH sensors, flame detectors, soil moisture sensors, and water level sensors—making it highly applicable for real-world industrial use cases.

Edge-IIoTset is segmented into two principal categories: normal and attack datasets. The attack dataset is composed of 14 individual CSV files, each representing a distinct type of cyberattack, including but not limited to

denial-of-service (DoS), distributed denial-of-service (DDoS), malware, injection, man-in-the-middle (MITM), and scanning attacks. The normal dataset consists of standard operational data gathered from the aforementioned sensors under non-malicious conditions. For the experiments presented in this study, two curated CSV files were primarily utilized: ‘ML-EdgeIIoT-dataset.csv’ and ‘DNN-EdgeIIoT-dataset.csv.’ The ML file comprises approximately 157,800 records, while the DNN file is significantly larger, containing about 2.2 million samples. These records reflect both benign and attack traffic across various IIoT devices and are representative of the complex dynamics found in industrial networks.

The dataset originally contains 63 features, but for the purposes of this research, feature selection was performed to reduce redundancy and improve model performance. Specifically, host-specific identifiers such as IP addresses and static frame attributes were eliminated, leaving 40 essential features that significantly contribute to accurate attack classification. These retained features capture key network statistics, sensor measurements, and communication patterns relevant to security threat detection. Ultimately, Edge-IIoTset offers a challenging yet realistic benchmark for evaluating the efficacy of machine learning and deep learning models in detecting cyber threats across diverse industrial settings. Its comprehensive structure makes it a valuable resource for developing next-generation intrusion detection systems tailored for IIoT applications.

IV. Methodology and Implementation

This section outlines the full pipeline for implementing SmartSentry’s intrusion detection framework. It details all preprocessing steps, algorithmic techniques, and experimental configurations used to train and evaluate the system on the Edge-IIoTset dataset.

Framework Overview

The proposed methodology follows a systematic workflow designed to handle the unique challenges of IIoT security. The key stages include data preprocessing, handling imbalanced datasets, feature engineering, model training, validation, and evaluation.

Experimental Setup

The system was implemented using Python 3.11 and Jupyter Notebook on a machine equipped with an Intel Core i5-1135G7 CPU and 16GB of RAM. This configuration ensured sufficient computational resources to process the Edge-IIoTset dataset efficiently.

Data Preprocessing

The raw dataset underwent several preprocessing stages:

- **Feature Reduction:** Static and redundant features, such as host identifiers, IP addresses, and frame-based attributes, were eliminated as they did not contribute to attack detection. This reduced the dimensionality while preserving relevant information.
- **Missing Values & Duplicates:** Null values and duplicate records were removed to ensure data consistency and prevent biased model training.
- **Shuffling:** The dataset was randomized to improve the representativeness of training and test samples.

Dummy Encoding

Categorical features were converted to numerical representations using dummy encoding (one-hot encoding). This transformation ensures compatibility with machine learning algorithms by preventing unintended ordinal interpretations of categorical data. Features such as `http.request.method`, `http.referer`, and `mqtt.protoname` were encoded into binary vectors.

Addressing Class Imbalance

To counteract class imbalance, the Synthetic Minority Oversampling Technique (SMOTE) was applied. SMOTE generates synthetic samples for minority classes by interpolating between existing samples, ensuring the classifier is not biased towards dominant classes.

Data Splitting and Scaling

The dataset was split into 80% training and 20% testing subsets. Feature scaling was then performed using Standard Scaling, normalizing all features to have zero mean and unit variance. This is particularly beneficial for distance-based models like KNN and SVM.

Feature Selection with PCA

Principal Component Analysis (PCA) was applied to further reduce dimensionality and retain key variance within the dataset. PCA helped to streamline model complexity and improve training efficiency while preserving critical patterns for threat detection.

Model Development

Multiple classifiers were implemented and compared:

1. **Decision Tree (DT)**: A simple yet interpretable model prone to overfitting in complex datasets.
2. **Random Forest (RF)**: An ensemble of decision trees that reduces overfitting and improves generalization.
3. **Extra Trees Classifier (ETC)**: Similar to RF but with additional randomness, offering faster training and competitive performance.
4. **Support Vector Machine (SVM)**: A powerful classifier for high-dimensional data, sensitive to feature scaling.
5. **k-Nearest Neighbors (KNN)**: A non-parametric model relying on distance metrics, effective in low-dimensional spaces.
6. **Deep Neural Network (DNN)**: A multi-layer feedforward neural network designed to capture complex data relationships with superior performance in multiclass detection.

Validation Strategy

A 10-fold cross-validation scheme was employed to assess each model's ability to generalize to unseen data. This method divides the dataset into 10 subsets, iteratively using one subset for testing while training on the remaining nine.

Implementation Summary : The entire workflow was streamlined via modular pipelines:

- Machine learning models (DT, RF, ETC, SVM, KNN) were trained on the "ML-EdgeIIoT-dataset.csv" file.

- The DNN model was trained on the larger "DNN-EdgeIIoT-dataset.csv" file, optimizing it for deep learning workloads.
- Cross-validation and performance metrics were consistently applied across all experiments to ensure comparability.

Fig. 1: IIoT Framework representation

V. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

This section highlights the findings of the proposed framework, Smart Sentry, focusing on multiple evaluation metrics. The performance is assessed using confusion matrices, key classification metrics (accuracy, precision, recall, F1-score), AUC-ROC analysis, k-fold cross-validation, and time complexity evaluations.

Fig. 2: Home Pages Of Smart Sentry

Fig 3: Interface of Remote user Login

Fig 4: Prediction Of Cyber Attack Type By User

Fig. 5: User Profile Details View Page

Fig 6: Browse, Test & Train Datasets

Fig. 11: Prediction of Cyber Attack Ratio

Fig. 12: Cyber Attack Type Ratio Result In Line Chart

Fig. 13: Cyber Attack Type Ratio Results In Pie Chart

Fig. 14: View All Remote Users In Service Provider

Confusion Matrix Analysis

Confusion matrices provide a detailed view of classifier performance by comparing predicted versus actual classifications. For binary classification, the proposed models achieve perfect matrices, indicating no false positives or negatives. In the multiclass (6-class and 15-class) tasks, the Deep Neural Network (DNN) model demonstrates exceptional capability, with minimal misclassifications. Specifically, misclassifications for the 6-class task largely involve confusion between malware and injection attacks, while in the 15-class task, minor overlap exists between closely related threat types such as port scanning and vulnerability scanning.

Classification Metrics

Across binary, 6-class, and 15-class tasks, DNN outperforms other machine learning models in accuracy and F1-score. For binary classification, DNN achieves 100% accuracy. For multiclass scenarios, DNN delivers 96.15% accuracy (6-class) and 94.68% accuracy (15-class), outperforming classical models like Random Forest and SVM. Other classifiers, while competent in binary scenarios, show reduced efficiency as the number of classes increases, underscoring the DNN's superior ability to generalize across complex datasets.

Model Learning Trends

Training and validation curves indicate effective model convergence. For binary classification, accuracy peaks early and stabilizes, with training and validation loss approaching zero. Similar patterns are observed in 6-class and 15-class cases, where the model maintains consistent learning across epochs without overfitting or underfitting tendencies.

AUC-ROC Curves

All models report near-ideal AUC-ROC scores, with DNN achieving an AUC of 1.0 across all classification tasks. This indicates the model's high discriminatory power in differentiating between threat categories, even in multiclass settings.

Cross-Validation Insights

10-fold cross-validation reaffirms the model's robustness. DNN consistently achieves the highest validation scores—1.0 for binary classification, 0.96 for 6-class, and 0.94 for 15-class classification. This demonstrates the model's capability to generalize well to unseen data and reduces the likelihood of overfitting.

Time Complexity Assessment

Time efficiency is critical for real-time threat detection in IIoT environments. The DNN model, while slightly more computationally intensive during training, offers significantly lower inference times during testing. Machine learning models such as Decision Trees and Random Forests exhibit faster training times but do not match DNN's performance on multiclass detection tasks.

Comparative Analysis

When benchmarked against existing state-of-the-art solutions, SmartSentry surpasses prior work in terms of accuracy, generalization, and speed. The proposed model outshines existing studies in both performance metrics

and resource efficiency, making it highly suitable for deployment in industrial IoT environments of SmartSentry in Industrial Sensor Networks

In modern industrial environments, environmental sensors such as flame detectors, pH meters, ultrasonic sensors, water level monitors, and temperature/humidity sensors play a crucial role in ensuring operational efficiency and safety compliance. However, their integration into IIoT networks has made them increasingly vulnerable to cyber threats, including data manipulation, denial-of-service (DoS) attacks, and unauthorized access attempts. Smart Sentry is proposed as a practical solution to secure these networks. Deployed at the edge, Smart Sentry can continuously monitor sensor data traffic and detect malicious activities in real-time using its machine learning and deep learning-based intrusion detection capabilities. The system is lightweight and can be integrated into existing industrial gateways, protecting both the data acquisition and transmission phases.

In this context, Smart Sentry's DNN model is particularly well-suited due to its ability to detect complex patterns in network traffic with low inference times. The model's high classification accuracy, demonstrated in binary, 6-class, and 15-class experiments, suggests its suitability for securing large-scale sensor deployments across industries such as manufacturing, energy, and water treatment facilities.

With its efficient detection mechanism, Smart Sentry can mitigate risks such as:

- Unauthorized control of actuators and devices.
- Injection of false readings to disrupt decision-making systems.
- Tampering with safety-critical parameters, like pH or temperature thresholds, which could lead to hazardous outcomes.

VI. Conclusion and Future Work

This study introduces Smart Sentry, a machine learning and deep learning-driven intrusion detection framework optimized for IIoT environments. The proposed system achieved excellent results across multiple classification levels, with the Deep Neural Network (DNN) model consistently outperforming traditional machine learning classifiers.

Key contributions of this research include:

- A modular framework incorporating PCA, SMOTE, and Standard Scaling to enhance model performance.
- Comparative analysis across multiple ML/DL models on the Edge-IIoTset dataset.
- Validation through k-fold cross-validation to ensure generalization and robustness.

The results confirm the effectiveness of Smart Sentry in detecting a broad range of cyber threats with high accuracy and reduced computational complexity, making it practical for real-time industrial applications.

For future work, several promising directions include:

1. **Hyperparameter Tuning:** Implementing advanced tuning techniques like Grid SearchCV to further optimize model configurations.
2. **Lightweight Deep Learning Architectures:** Exploring the deployment of lightweight DNN models such as MobileNet or TinyML for resource-constrained IIoT devices.
3. **Alternative Feature Selection Methods:** Investigating other dimensionality reduction techniques like Recursive Feature Elimination (RFE) or Autoencoder-based selection.

4. **Real-world Deployment:** Integrating Smart Sentry into live IIoT systems to evaluate its performance under actual cyberattack scenarios.
5. **Broader Dataset Evaluation:** Extending experiments to additional public IIoT datasets to improve the model's generalizability.

The research contributes meaningfully to the field of IIoT cybersecurity and paves the way for more resilient, scalable, and intelligent IDS solutions tailored to evolving industrial threats.

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